

From: B [REDACTED] A [REDACTED] A [REDACTED]

To: **The Clerk to the Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs**

Subject: **Memorandum on the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill**

Date: **October 6, 2021**

1.0 Introduction:

I write in response to the request put out by the Parliament of Ghana on 15th September 2021 asking for written Memoranda on 3 bills before Parliament. We intend to focus on the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill.

I write as a citizen of this country, the son of a petty trader and classroom teacher, whose toil and sweat have pushed me to become a responsible contributor to our country this day. Anyone who went through a boys' school in Ghana can testify with certainty that their efforts and that of others like them could have been foiled if the reprehensible activities and advocacy of those who support the LGBT+ lifestyle was condoned in such environments.

2.0 Core Issues:

If you or your ward(s) have been to a boys' school (and for that matter any single sex school) and you were sexually harassed or raped by someone who belonged to this community of aggressive oppressors, I can assure you that you wouldn't even think of granting a hearing to anyone who wants to suggest that their choice of lifestyle is a right, much less something that they should be allowed to impose of others like they are presently attempting to do.

Maybe we again want scenes in which secondary school boys were ready and willing to kill other boys because they harassed them sexually.

Maybe we want to see scenes in which secondary school boys are raped by other boys in school, and because of the embarrassment and stigma attached to rape, they live with the vendetta and hatred, and spread same all their lives.

Maybe we want to have students who go to senior high school just to return with sexually transmitted diseases which ruin the rest of their entire lives.

Maybe we want students who get hooked on to these practices and begin to decline in their academic performance because of lack of concentration.

Maybe we just want to shatter the future of young innocent people by suggesting to their minds that they are what they are not, and allowing people to impose of them ideologies that will alter their lives irreparably.

Maybe we want to open the door to import a new sort of colonialism which is preceded by brainwashing young people and getting them morally bankrupt so they can destroy themselves from within.

What I am saying is this:

- i. Anyone who chooses to be a homosexual (gay or lesbian) is taking a personal decision which must not be imposed on any other person.
- ii. Such behavior is much more costly to society than our country can ever bear in all of its existence.
- iii. Anyone who chooses to change their sex is as going against scientific research which shows that their personal choices does not change who they truly are. If they thus assay to act like who they are not just because they so identity, it doesn't change the fact that they inconvenience and even put into danger other people. If I identify as a woman and so insist on being admitted to Aburi girls' senior high school, we can only imagine how crazy such a world would be.
- iv. Everyone who identifies him/herself as anything must keep that as a personal choice, and not insist on everyone accepting that they are what their physiology doesn't say they are.

If we reject this bill, we may as well be on our way to creating an army of young people who will do worse than Reinhard Sinaga, Britain's most notorious rapist who single handed committed sexual violence against about 190 victims. This young man is reported to have raped at least 136 young men between 2015 and 2017 in Manchester where he was living as a student. Maybe, this is what we want to invite to Ghana. Just maybe.

I therefore fully endorse the PPHSRGFV Bill and encourage parliament and the president to fully pass it without delay.

Teaching Assistant,